

THE REFLECTION OF NATIONAL-CULTURAL LEXICON IN ABDULLA QAKHHOR'S WORKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776239>

Abstract. The article describes the rich lexical units of Uzbek language and the specific features of the national-cultural lexicon in the works of A. Qakhhor. Examples from the story "Tales from the Past" are also analyzed.

Keywords: national-cultural lexicon, idiom, onomastics, history, philosophy, ethnography, cultural studies.

The national culture of a particular people mainly refers to the ethnic aspects of that ethnic group, the national worldview, customs, rules of etiquette, norms of communication developed in relation with historical traditions, examples of creativity that reflect the national spirit, proverbs, sayings, phrases, figurative expressions, figurative units and others are understood. It is characteristic that the national-cultural sign is reflected differently in language units. Some units directly show the sign of national identity, while in some units this sign appears indirectly. In some words, the cultural meaning coexists with the lexical meaning, while in some words, it appears through their figurative meaning. For example, since expressions reflect reality through figurative meaning, they directly reflect a national-cultural sign. Or the realities that are unique to a certain language also contain the signs specific to that language. An example of this is the lexeme **bashik**. In proverbs such as "*Beshik bolasi — bek bolasi*", "*Beshikdagi besh turlanar, Qayoqqa bursang, shunga o'rganar*", "*Bola beshikdan yiqilguncha, Podsho taxtidan yiqilsin*", "*Bola bo'lsa, beshik topilar*", etc.; national-cultural symbols characteristic of Uzbek people can be seen in such compound words as *beshikkertti* (the custom of betrothing children in their cradles), *beshikso'poq* (head with a flat occiput due to long, monotonous sleeping in the cradle), or in the word *beshiktervatar* it can be seen that the behavior of this insect has been compared to rocking a cradle, thus it has got this name. *Beshiktervatar* cannot be translated word for word into other languages, its alternative in Russian is "богомол" (it is believed that this name was given because the insect resembles a person praying); in English, Spanish is "mantis" (etymological meaning means "god, seer, prophet"¹), the name of mantis in these languages is connected to religious interpretation. It is understood that the name of this insect was dominated by a religious scene (bogomol, mantis) in

¹ <https://www.etymonline.com/word/mantis>

some ethnic groups, and a national-cultural scene (beshik) prevailed in Uzbek language. As noted by B. Tojiboyev, “The lexeme "beshik" in Uzbek language is considered a national-cultural unit because it directly reflects the object that has become one of the national values of Uzbek people. In such a situation, the sign of culture specific to the language unit is understood through its dictionary meaning. Such units are historically formed, occupy an important place in the cultural life of the nation, and are not observed in other languages”². For this reason, **beshiktervatar** is considered a purely national term in the onomastics of Uzbek language.

In the works of art, there are such national-cultural lexical units that represent the culture, values, traditions, mentality, and customs of the people to which the work belongs, that it is always difficult to find alternative options in their translation. The richness of Uzbek language is reflected in the works of A. Qakhhor. The reader feels like falling into the depicted reality. Thus, the writer further developed the short story genre with his works. The reason for his frequent reference to this genre is the fact that small genres are operative compared to epic genres in responding to the events of the period. Being faithful to the traditions of realism, the writer expresses the pain of the people in his works and looks after their interests. That is why the reader who reads his works is deeply affected.

In all the works of A. Qakhhor, a lot of national-cultural lexicon typical of Uzbek people can be found, for example, in the text of "Tales from the Past": *“Hovliga yig‘lab kirdim. Onam yuragi yorilguday bo‘lib yuzimga suv sepdi, ho‘l ko‘ylagimni yechib tashlash ham esiga kelmay, latta yoqib boshimdan aylantirib tashladi-**alasladi**. Shundan keyin bir hafta ko‘chaga chiqqani ijozat bo‘lmadi. Yana bir kuni, eshigimiz oldida **loyparsilloq** o‘ynab o‘tirgan edim. Bularning **kizagi** qizil ko‘k shapkasiga, chakkasida hurpayib turgan sochiga, kiyim-boshi va **shop-sholopiga** qarab angrayganimcha ergashib ketaveribman”³*, the variants “olos-olos”, “oloslamoq”, “alas-alas qilmoq or olos-olos qilmoq” of the verb **alasladi/moq** are also widely used in fiction and folklore. In the explanatory dictionary, two different uses of this lexeme are mentioned: 1. To turn a burning rag or the patient's clothes over the head of the patient in order to “cure” a bedridden patient; 2. To light a bonfire and jump over it in the month of Safar in

² Tojiboyev B. Milliy-madaniy birliklar tilning milliy o‘ziga xosligini namoyon qiluvchi birliklar sifatida // O‘zbek tilini dunyo miqyosida keng targ‘ib qilish bo‘yicha hamkorlik istiqbollari mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. – Toshkent, 2020. – P. 55.

³ Абдулла Қаҳҳор. Ўтмишдан эртақлар. –ТОШКЕНТ:Янги Аср Авлоди. 2017. – P.23

order to get rid of demons, fiend, etc., which are attached to a person ⁴. Also national-cultural language units belonging to Uzbek lexicography such as *loyparsilloq*, *kizagi* can be found in the passage. A translator who is ignorant of national customs, culture, and history will have many problems when translating these words into another language or finding lexemes with a meaning close to the original. It is necessary for a translator to know which method serves to deliver the translation to the reader as fully as the original content. “*Kizagi*”, “*kizak*” in the text – is considered as the part between the top and the brim of the cap (*duppi*), the flange⁵. “The word *Kizak* etymologically means “bunchy”, “bent place” and hypocoristic for the Tajik word “eye”, made adding the suffix *-ak* and the sound *-o’* has been replaced with the sound *-i* in Uzbek language”⁶. Sometimes the national-cultural meaning, historical process, etymological meaning of the word is forgotten, and the main attention is focused on the sentence that comes after it, and in this case on the word “*blue hat*” and usually it is possible that such a basic national-cultural lexicon (in this case, *kizagi qizil*) is “forgotten” in the translation.

In conclusion, Abdulla Qakhor beautifully reflects the national-cultural lexicon through his rich and evocative storytelling. Through his writing, Qakhor captures the essence of his culture, traditions, and history, providing readers with a deep and insightful exploration of the national identity. His use of language, imagery, and symbolism effectively conveys the unique characteristics and values of his homeland, creating a powerful connection between his works and the national-cultural heritage. Qakhor's ability to weave these elements seamlessly into his narratives showcases his talent as a writer and his dedication to preserving and celebrating his cultural roots. Overall, the reflection of the national-cultural lexicon in the works of Abdulla Qakhor serves as a testament to the enduring significance and beauty of his literary contributions.

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⁴ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5 жилдлик. «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси». – Тошкент: 2006-2008. 1-ж. – P.67

⁵ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5 жилдлик. «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси». – Тошкент: 2006-2008. 3-ж. – P.364

⁶ Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг этимологик луғати. – Тошкент, 2009. – P. 121.

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